

Supplemental Materials

Section S1. Supplemental Figures



Fig. S1. Location of the field test site and site photograph: (a) location map; (b) field photograph



Fig. S2. Pile and sensor layout diagram



Fig. S3. Pressure sensors installed on the shaft of the PHC pile